

KarstHives 2 - Climate Archives in Karst: The Final Workshop

“Understanding past climates and environments from karst deposits”

April 20-22, 2023, Sudrigiu, Romania

PROGRAM and ABSTRACTS

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Apuseni Natural Park

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“Cave deposits as archives of climate and environmental changes. A Center of Excellence in speleological research”

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PROGRAM

April 20, 2023

9:30 – Opening address

9:45 – Alin Moș¹: [Apuseni Natural Park – The Park of Karst.](#)

10:15 – Konstantin Kostov: [Protected karst phenomena in Bulgaria - problems of geoconservation.](#)

10:45 – Silviu Constantin: [An overview on the KARSTHIVES 2 project – achievements and unfinished businesses.](#)

11:15 – Coffee break

12:00 – Marius Robu, Ionuț-Cornel Mirea, Alexandru Petculescu, Marius Kenesz, Luchiana Faur, Laura Tîrlă, Oana Teodora Moldovan, Silviu Constantin: [Cave bear of Romania – A comprehensive view.](#)

12:30 – Cristian G. Panaiotu, Relu D. Roban, Cristian Necula, Ionut Mirea, Luchiana Faur, Alexandru Petculescu, Silviu Constantin: [The reliability of the magnetic signature of siliciclastic cave sediments as a proxy for environmental changes.](#)

13:00 – Alida Timar-Gabor, Aditi Dave, Zuzanna Kabacinska: [Advantages and limitation of using electron spin resonance for dating sediments.](#)

13:30 – Daniela Constantin, Anca Avram, Alida Timar-Gabor: [Luminescence dating of challenging samples.](#)

14:00 – Lunch

¹ Authors in **bold** are presenting.

15:00 – Robert Begy, Codrin Savin, Alida Timar-Gabor: [Air and water radon measurements in cave systems](#)

15:30 – Nimrod Marom, Roe Shafir: [Desert cave biogenic deposits and the Pleistocene climatic record of the Judean Desert](#)

16:00 – Marius Kenesz, Adrian Ruicănescu, Ignacio A. Lazagabaster, Uri Davidovich, Nimrod Marom, **Oana Teodora Moldovan**: [Can fossil beetles preserved in sediments bring new information on the paleoenvironment in the Dead Sea region? - the example of the Cave of Skulls.](#)

16:30 – Daniel Vereş, Marian Cosac, George Murătoreanu, Ştefan Vasile, Alexandru Petculescu, Valentin Dumitraşcu, Marius Robu, Loredana Niţă: [Middle Palaeolithic cave sequences in Eastern Transylvania, Romania.](#)

17:00 – Ştefan Vasile, Virgil Drăguşin, Alexandru Petculescu, Ionuţ Mirea, Silviu Constantin, Tiberiu Bogdan Sava, Gabriela Odilia Sava: [Herpetofaunal changes during the Late Pleistocene–Early Holocene transition – a case study from Isverna \(SW Romania\).](#)

17:30 – Alexandru Petculescu: [Small mammals from cave deposits and paleoclimate reconstructions during the Pleistocene.](#)

18:00 – End of session

19:00 – Steering committee meeting

20:00 – Dinner

April 21, 2023

9:30 – Christos Pennos, Rannveig Øvrevik Skoglund, Stein-Erik Lauritzen and Magnus Thorvik: [Aspfjordgrotta: a recorder of glacial-interglacial cycles](#).

10:00 – Maria-Laura Tîrlă, Ionuț-Cornel Mirea, Laurențiu Țuțuianu, Alexandru Călin, Virgil Drăgușin, Tiberiu Bogdan Sava, Maria Ilie, Cristian Mănăilescu: [Climatic oscillations of the last 35 ka recorded in sackung deposits of marble stripe karst \(Făgăraș Mountains, Southern Carpathians\)](#).

10:30 – Ionuț-Cornel Mirea, Marius Robu, Alexandru Petculescu, Marius Kenesz, Luchiana Faur, Răzvan Arghir, Silviu Constantin: [Late Pleistocene climate evolution in the Southern Carpathians recorded by cave deposits from Muierilor cave system \(Romania\)](#).

11:00 – Coffee break

11:30 – Marius Robu, Ionuț-Cornel Mirea, Alexandru Petculescu, Marius Kenesz, Luchiana Faur, William Pestle, Peter K. Swart, Silviu Constantin: [Palaeodiet and palaeoecology of a complex Late Pleistocene mammal association in the Romanian Carpathians](#).

12:00 – Silviu Constantin, Ali Pourmand, Arash Sharifi, Sevag Mehterian, Oana Teodora Moldovan, Peter K. Swart: [A high-resolution Holocene speleothem record from Tăușoare Cave, NE Romania: the nexus of Arctic and North Atlantic atmospheric circulations](#).

12:30 – Sandor Matyasi, Alexandru Petculescu, Ionut Mirea: [Experimental geoelectric measurements carried out in Ursilor Cave \(Apuseni Mountains\)](#).

13:00 -- Lunch

14:30 – 18:00 – visit to the Urșilor Cave

19:00 – 23:00 – Time for discussions, networking, and final dinner

April 22, 2023

7:30 – 11:00 – Travel to the Humpleu Cave

11:00 – 14:30 – Visit of the cave

15:00 – End of the workshop and travel to Cluj-Napoca

ABSTRACTS

Protected karst phenomena in Bulgaria - problems of geoconservation

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The karst study in Bulgaria began at the end of XIX-th century. The karst terrains are an important element of the geodiversity of the Bulgarian lands and cover 22.7% of the country's territory. Their high scientific, cognitive and aesthetic value is a significant part of the objects of the Bulgarian geological heritage. The karst in Bulgaria is developed in rocks with different age – from Proterozoic marble in the southern part of the country up to Neogene limestone in the NW Bulgaria.

The karst phenomena have been used since the emergence of the humans. Some of these uses are of considerable cultural significance. Of the impressive number of uses of karst landforms by man, in Bulgaria, the following groups are covered: (1) Water supply: The waters of about 40 Bulgarian caves and numerous karst springs are captured and water supply a significant number of settlements. More than 320 dams and other types of hydraulic constructions are directly or indirectly connected to karstified carbonate rocks; (2) Quarries for limestone and marble: Some quarries threaten karst landforms; (3) Different aspects of scientific research: Relatively few Bulgarian scientists are currently studying karst geology and geomorphology. A greater number are studying cave biodiversity; (4) Tourism and recreation in various forms: Twelve Bulgarian caves are being developed for mass tourist visits as electrified show caves. Several other caves are with guided tours with local cavers; (5) Food industry: Some underground karst landforms in Bulgaria are used for food production and aging; (6) Religious purposes: A considerable number of karst forms are known in Bulgaria - sanctuaries related to religious cults, doctrines and beliefs from antiquity to the present day; (7) Military goal: In this aspect, the enormous entrance chamber of the Devetaki Cave and the entrance parts of Emen Cave (North Bulgaria) were used as fuel depots of the Bulgarian Army during the Cold War time; (8) Medicine: It is well known the experiment of 1974 and 1975 for the treatment of bronchial asthma in Magura Cave, NW Bulgaria.

These uses result in a remarkable range of negative impacts – degradation of the physical structure of the karst landforms, alternation of the karst hydrology and microclimate. This paper deals with some problems connected to their protection, conservation and management. The problems are separated in theoretical and practical parts.

An overview on the KARSTHIVES 2 project – achievements and unfinished businesses.

Silviu Constantin

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The **Karsthives 2** project proposed an integrated approach to paleoclimate and paleoenvironmental studies based upon a multi-proxy analysis of the various archives from caves and karst deposits. We focused on proxies such as the stable isotopes in calcite and bone remains, chemical (trace elements), and mineralogical variations in speleothems, magnetic properties of fluvial or lacustrine sediments, fossil and sub-fossil species and faunal associations, stable isotopes and composition of the underground ice accumulations. Most of the above deposits bear information relevant for the paleoclimate evolution at regional scale and their high-resolution radiometric datings allow signal calibration and comparative analysis of the different time-series.

During the project we carried out systematic excavations at several caves such as Ursilor, Muierilor, Bisericuta, the caves of Varghis Gorge. We continued the study of fossil invertebrates from karst sediments such as the ones of the Zăton Lake, Grand Dolina (Spain), and Cave of Skulls (Israel). We have performed more than 60 U/Th datings on speleothems from caves in Romania and Bulgaria, and, for some specimens, stable isotope records have been measured. Attempts to calibrate the clumped isotope thermometer based on farmed calcite from a Romanian cave have been done at the Bergen University laboratories. A stable isotope study has been conducted on fossil remains of large mammals from the Muierilor Cave that shed light on the controversial diet of the cave bears.

Exploratory work has been done on ice caves such as Scarisoara (Romania) and Svarthammarhola (Norway). In one of the Romanian caves, we have encountered a handful of tools that may be attributed to the Upper Palaeolithic and work is in progress to understand the context of the human presence at this site. Further work has been done to understand the role of the microbial communities in mineralogenesis of cave formations. On a more applicative approach, we took advantage of our installed networks of cave microclimate monitoring to investigate the impact of tourism on the cave formations and underground water bodies.

The project has yielded, so far, a number of 38 publications and the ongoing works hold the promise of more than 10 other to be published in the coming years. However, in spite of these achievements, there are still plenty of open topics that need further work, more financing, and time to make it to their respective journals.

Cave bear of Romania – A comprehensive view

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Fossils of cave bears are the most frequent findings among the Upper Pleistocene extinct megafauna, from the cave deposits of Romania. Here we summarize the results of almost 20 years of cave bear research at the “Emil Racoviță” Institute of Speleology (ERIS), following some main directions – age dating and palaeoecology. The vast majority of the radiometric data of the cave bear remains (N = 96) across Romania belongs to the Marine Isotope Stage 3 (MIS 3) period (*ca.* 60-25 ka BP). Almost 170 (N = 171) adult cave bears were investigated by means of $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ suggesting dietary variability among the studied populations. So far, cave bear fossils have been found in deposits of more than 170 localities from the Romanian Carpathians. This study also provides updated data on the geographical distribution of the MIS 3 cave bear sites in Romania. At the moment, the Romanian Carpathians provided the richest dataset on the palaeoecology of the Eurasian Late Pleistocene cave bears. The majority of the generated data were made through KARSTHIVES I and II projects.

The reliability of the magnetic signature of siliciclastic cave sediments as a proxy for environmental changes

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Several studies have shown that the magnetic susceptibility data of cave sediment can be used to reconstruct paleoenvironment outside the cave at the time of deposition. These magnetic susceptibility variations are attributed to soils with climate-dependent magnetic properties that are washed, blown, or tracked into the cave where they accumulate, creating the changes observed in rock magnetic data. Most of these studies were done on cave entrance facies where the influence of the climate is stronger. To test if this hypothesis is valid also for interior facies deposited deep into the cave, we have measured both the magnetic properties of cave sediments and of the soils in surrounding areas. We selected three Romanian caves where we have some control over the age of the siliciclastic sediments: Peștera cu Oase (Panaiotu et al., 2013), Urșilor (Constantin et al., 2014), and Muierii (Mirea et al., 2021). The soils developed in the areas of these caves show various degrees of magnetic enhancement produced by pedogenesis. These soils are mixt during their transport into the cave by water, so mean values of their magnetic properties are relevant for the interpretations. The mean values recorded by the present-day soils can be considered as an indicator of the degree of magnetic enhancement produced by climate during an interglacial. Comparing the magnetic properties of recent soils with those of the corresponding cave sediments, we concluded that only the large values recorded in the cave sediments similar to the present-day soil values can be interpreted as an indication of the erosion of an interglacial soils. Lower values are more difficult to interpret in terms of climate because they can reflect both fewer soils transported into the cave or a cold environment which has inhibited the magnetic enhancement of the soils.

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References

- Constantin S., Robu M., Munteanu C-M, Petculescu A., Vlaicu M., Mirea I., Kenesz M., Drăgusiu V., Hoffman D., Anechitei V., Timar-Gabor A., Roban R-D, Panaiotu C. G., 2014. Reconstructing the evolution of cave systems as a key to understanding the taphonomy of fossil accumulations: The case of Ursilor Cave (Western Carpathians, Romania), *Quaternary International*, 339-340, 25-40.
- Mirea I-C., Robu M., Petculescu A., Kenesz M., Faur L., Arghir R., Tecsa V., Timar-Gabor A., Roban R-D., Panaiotu C.G., Sharifi A., Pourmand A., Codrea V. A., Constantin S., 2021. Last deglaciation flooding events in the Southern Carpathians as revealed by the study of cave deposits from Muierilor Cave, Romania, *Palaeogeography, Palaeoclimatology, Palaeoecology*, 562, 110084.
- Panaiotu, C., Constantin, S., Petrea, C., Horoi, V., Panaiotu, C-E., 2013. Rock Magnetic Data of Late Pleistocene Sediments from the Peștera cu Oase and Their Paleoclimatic Significance. In: Erik Trinkaus, Silviu Constantin, João Zilhão (eds), *Life and Death at the Peștera cu Oase, A Setting for Modern Human Emergence in Europe*, Oxford University Press, pp. 86-99.

Advantages and limitation of using electron spin resonance for dating sediments

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In many luminescence and electron spin resonance (ESR) dating studies the choice of grain size fraction used for analysis has been most often dictated predominantly by the nature and availability of the material.

While most ESR dating studies focus on the use of coarse quartz grains that are generally larger than 63 μm , such fraction is very scarce in cave sediments. Consequently, we have documented the possibility of using fine quartz grains for dating, namely the 4-11 μm fraction. We examined the spectra of fine (4-11 μm) and coarse (63-90, 125-180 μm) sedimentary quartz separates extracted from previously well-characterised samples. We conclude that Al-hole ($[\text{AlO}_4/\text{h}]^0$) measurements of fine grains are affected by the presence of peroxy signals to a much bigger extent than coarse grains. To avoid this, we propose a new approach to amplitude measuring method, focusing on the peak-to-baseline amplitude of the part of the signal at $g \approx 2.0603$ that has the potential of providing more accurate results [1].

Recreating a response of a crystalline material to natural radiation by means of artificial irradiation in laboratory is one of the basic assumptions of trapped charge dating methods. Other important properties of signals that affect the accuracy of electron spin resonance (ESR) dating include dose response curve saturation [2,3], bleaching properties [4] and thermal stability [3].

Based on our studies, we conclude that the upper age limit for ESR dating using Al and Ti related signals corresponds to about 1500 Gy (i.e 750 ka for a dose rate of 2.5 Gy/ka or 300 ka for a dose rate of 5 Gy/ka) and bleaching corrections are mandatory.

References:

1. Kabacińska, Timar-Gabor, A., 2022. Dating sediments by EPR using Al-h centre: a comparison between the properties of fine (4-11 μm) and coarse (> 60 μm) quartz grains. *Molecules*, 27(9), 2683.
2. Benzid, K., Timar-Gabor, A., 2020. Phenomenological model of aluminium-hole ($[\text{AlO}_4/\text{h}^+]^0$) defect formation in sedimentary quartz upon room temperature irradiation: electron spin resonance (ESR) study, *Radiation Measurements*, 130,106187.
3. Kabacińska, Z., Buylaert, J.P., Yi, S., Timar-Gabor, A., 2022. Revisiting natural and laboratory electron spin resonance (ESR) dose response curves of quartz from Chinese loess. *Quaternary Geochronology*, 70, 101306.
4. Timar-Gabor, A., Chruścińska, A., Benzid, K., Fitzsimmons, K., Begy, R., Bailey, M., 2020. Bleaching studies on Al-hole ($[\text{AlO}_4/\text{h}]^0$) electron spin resonance (ESR) signal in sedimentary quartz, *Radiation Measurements*, 130,106221

Luminescence dating of challenging samples

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Luminescence dating is an important numerical-age technique used in Quaternary research that uses the light emissions in the constituent minerals to determine the time elapsed since their last exposure to daylight. Loess and cave deposits are regarded as valuable paleoenvironmental archives and their paleoclimate significance is revealed by luminescence chronologies.

One of the most important assumptions of optically stimulated luminescence (OSL) is the resetting (bleaching) of previously incorporated luminescence signal before sediment deposition. Quartz is the preferred dosimeter due to its high bleachability and is usually dated by the application of the Single Aliquot Regenerative dose (SAR) protocol [1]. Signal resetting in quartz extracted from cave deposits may be challenging due to the short sedimentation history and the absence of exposure to sunlight for a long period. However, by applying SAR protocol on 63–90 μm quartz we reported a robust luminescence ages ranging from 55 ± 6 ka to 122 ± 19 ka for Muierilor Cave, Romania [2].

Loess deposits are considered ideal for luminescence dating due to their eolian origin which ensures a complete signal resetting. Yet, in South Island of New Zealand, the applicability of OSL dating has been previously hampered by the weak sensitivity of the luminescence signal and poor behaviour in the SAR protocol when using coarse ($> 63 \mu\text{m}$) quartz extracts. By applying luminescence dating on fine (4–11 μm) quartz we observed a satisfactory behaviour in the SAR protocol and we obtained robust ages ranging from 0.300 ± 0.004 ka to 16 ± 1 ka [3].

Overall, our results indicate that the SAR protocol can be successfully applied in challenging environments by examining the different properties of different grain sizes of quartz.

References:

1. Murray, A.S., Wintle, A.G., 2000. Luminescence dating using an improved single-aliquot regenerative-dose protocol. *Radiation Measurements*, 32, 57–73.
2. Mirea, I.C., Robu, M., Petculescu, A., Kenesz, M., Faur, L., Arghir, R., Tecsa, V., Timar-Gabor, A., Roban, R.-S., Panaiotu, C.G., Sharifi, A., Codrea, V.A., Constantin, S., 2021. Last deglaciation flooding events in the Southern Carpathians as revealed by the study of cave deposits from Muierilor Cave, Romania. *Palaeogeography, Palaeoclimatology, Palaeoecology*, 562, 110084.
3. Avram, A., Kabacinska, Z., Micallef, A., Timar-Gabor, A., 2022. Testing the potential of using quartz for dating loess in South Island, New Zealand. *Radiation Measurements*, 155, 106788.

Air and water radon measurements in cave systems

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Caves accumulate naturally high concentrations of radon gas and its progenies, which may reach levels from several times to several thousand times higher than outdoor air concentrations. This allows for the investigation of radon behavior, formation, and seasonal/diurnal variation patterns driven by bi-directional convective ventilation. Furthermore, the study of cave climates with reference to air circulation as well as the recharge dynamics of karst aquifers are possible by using radon as the main tracer for these environmental processes. The applications of radon measurements in cave environments are extensive and require reliable methods to assure the quality of the results. Besides passive methods, the active and semi-passive techniques enable fast and continuous measurements that allow for high temporal-resolution data collection of variation patterns, as well as records of minor changes in radon gas concentration.

As caves possess particular properties in terms of water and air gas composition, carbon dioxide and hydrogen sulfide of moffetic origin are present in varying concentrations. The presence of these gases may influence the counting efficiency of the measurement devices and return erroneous results. Experimental results revealed severe underestimations of radon results returned by electrostatic collection cell devices in the presence of CO₂ and H₂S in water and air. A concentration of 1.29 g/L of CO₂ in the water sample led to an average 25% decrease in the ²²²Rn measured value, while 0.5 mg/L H₂S reached a 43% underestimation of radon activity when compared to the gas-free samples. These results are highlighting the importance of developing improved methodologies and procedures that are adapted to be suitable to the environment presented by caves, to ensure the accuracy of measurements without renouncing the benefits of active methods. Different correction methods (mathematical/chemical) can be employed to remove the effects of other gases on radon measurements in caves [1], however, the development of specific sampling and measurement protocols can prove to reduce the uncertainties to an acceptable degree. Semi-passive methods can provide time-effective measurements similar to active methods, without the risk of interferences caused by CO₂ and H₂S gases on the counting efficiency of the devices. Scintillation Counting techniques may represent a viable alternative for the study of radon in caves, either by diffusion or bubbling of air into a scintillator cocktail, or the use of modified Lucas cells with a less reactive ZnS(Ag) coating. In terms of quality assurance and accuracy of the results, the development of improved and adapted radon measurement protocols and techniques proves to be mandatory for the proper study of cave environments and radon dynamics.

References:

1. Begy, R.C., Savin, C., Timar-Gabor, A., 2022. Correction of the effects of carbon dioxide and hydrogen sulfide on electrostatic cell monitors measurements of radon in water. *Journal of Environmental Chemical Engineering*, 10, 107040.

Desert cave biogenic deposits and the Pleistocene climatic record of the Judean Desert

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The caves of the Judean desert contain numerous biogenic animal bones assemblages. In the last four years we conducted a systematic paleozoological survey of 60 caves, and radiocarbon dated more than 120 mammal bones. Following taxonomic identification with aDNA and geometric morphometrics, we use species distribution modelling to track Pleistocene climatic fluctuations in the region during key points from ~400kya to the middle Holocene. Our results suggest that some woodland persisted from MIS5 to MIS3, giving way to cold desert in the LGM. Following a somewhat wetter early Holocene, hot desert conditions have probably set in after the local Chalcolithic, by the middle of the fourth millennium BCE. This independent dataset affords a new perspective on the environmental history of an important part of the corridor crossing the Levant from Africa.

Can fossil beetles preserved in sediments bring new information on the paleoenvironment in the Dead Sea region? - the example of the Cave of Skulls

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The southern part of the Levant supposedly had savanna-like environments that acted as a dispersal corridor for fauna and humans from Africa to the eastern Mediterranean region during the Pleistocene. Evidence of more densely vegetated areas in what today is an arid region in the southern Judean Desert was found in the Cave of the Skulls. Well-preserved fossils of a now extinct subspecies of the eastern African crested rat (*Lophiomys imhausi marmortum*) dated to 42 ka–103 ka were found in the cave alongside fossil remains of bears, cervids, and arboreal squirrels, suggesting that the steep, rocky valleys of the region once sustained woodlands vegetation (Lazagabaster et al., 2021). To gain insights in the ancient paleoenvironments of the region, we describe the beetle remains of a remaining sedimentary sequence of the Cave of the Skulls.

Five samples of sediments were taken from the cave in a side passage where vertebrate fossils were also abundant. The samples belong to four levels with an interval between 39,930±240 and 40,240±170 years (uncalibrated ¹⁴C dates). Samples were sorted in the laboratory under the microscope after sieving them through successive net sizes of 200, 125 and 63 µm. Fragments belonging to small vertebrate bones, teeth, plant fragments, and fossil invertebrates were found. From the fossil invertebrates, most of the fragments belong to the surface beetle (Coleoptera; Figure 1). So far, one of us (AR) has identified two genera among the sorted fragments (*Sitophilus* and *Cheirodes*). *Sitophilus* is a weevil genus (Curculionidae) with 14 species distributed worldwide. The best-known species destroy stored wheat, rice, sorghum, oats etc., while other species use the acorns of oak and other tree seeds. *Cheirodes* belonging to the Tenebrionidae family (darkling beetles) are typical for grasslands and shrublands. The preliminary results suggest that around the time when the crested rat disappeared from the region, trees may have been still present in the region. We will further discuss the implications of the presence of these genera and the correlation with other paleoenvironmental proxies during MIS3 in the region.

References

Lazagabaster IA, Rovelli V, Fabre PH, Porat R, Ullman M, Davidovich U, Lavi T, Ganor A, Klein E, Weiss K, Nuriel P, Meiri M, Marom N. 2021. Rare crested rat subfossils unveil Afro–Eurasian ecological corridors synchronous with early human dispersals. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America* **118**: e2105719118.

Figure 1. Examples of beetle fragments that were found in the sediment samples from the Cave of the Skulls.

Middle Palaeolithic cave sequences in Eastern Transylvania, Romania

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The Middle to Upper Palaeolithic transition has been one of the critical periods of change in the prehistory of Europe. It has witnessed the full emergence, continent-wide of modern human technologies, detrimental of Neanderthal survival. Knowledge about the transition is significant, however, the evidence for cultural and technological developments in the Carpathian area is still rather sparse, particularly in what concerns the Middle Palaeolithic.

Here we present results of chronological and sedimentological investigations of several Middle Palaeolithic cave contexts (P. Gabor, P. Mare, Abri 122, P. Ursului) within the Varghis karst, eastern Transylvania, Romania. Archaeological results indicate several stages of Middle Palaeolithic habitation in the area. Reanalysis of the deeper stratigraphy previously unexcavated within Abri 122 shows that at least two main anthropogenic horizons have been preserved. In both horizons, the bone assemblages (Bos/Bison, Capra, Canis lupus, Ursus spaeleus) directly associated with lithics point to human-accumulation of material.

To augment the typological cultural considerations of Abri 122 we applied direct radiocarbon dating on bones and charcoals from within the occupation layers. Radiocarbon dating on bones suggests the lowermost occupation layer is >43.4 radiocarbon kyr BP old, whereas infrared stimulated luminescence (IRSL) ages on the lowermost productive layer and above it indicate surprisingly old ages of ca. 120 kyr and respectively, ca. 70 kyr. Multiple protocol dating of charcoal found within the two habitation layers also produced ages >38 radiocarbon kyr BP, suggesting that the lowermost habitation layer unequivocally pertains to the Middle Palaeolithic industries. The upper habitation level is generally marked by a high percentage of lithics. Overall, the recovered lithics, currently forming one of the most significant collections of this sort for the area, are consistent with two main habitation phases connected to Middle Palaeolithic cultural affinities. Chronological investigations (such as radiocarbon, OSL/IRSL dating, tephrochronology) carried out in P. Gabor, P. Mare, P. Ursului caves generally support this interpretation.

**Herpetofaunal changes during the Late Pleistocene–Early Holocene transition
– a case study from Isverna (SW Romania)**

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Palaeontological excavations that took place in Stoieni Cave (Isverna, Mehedinți County) yielded numerous megafaunal remains, drawing attention to the high potential of small vertebrates to exist as well. Screen washing the sediment from six depth intervals indeed produced a large amount of small vertebrate remains. The herpetofaunal assemblages include rare indeterminate fish vertebrae, but also amphibian (*Triturus cristatus*, *Bufo viridis*, *Bufo bufo*, *Pelophylax esculentus*), and reptile (*Anguis colchica*, *Lacerta viridis*, *Lacerta agilis*, *Elaphe quatuorlineata*, *Natrix natrix*, *Vipera ammodytes*) specimens. Most identified taxa are still present in the area, and prefer warm temperate or sub-Mediterranean climate. However, comparing specimen abundance in each of the investigated depth intervals, it becomes clear that some intervals were more inhospitable to herpetofaunas, and, in one case, completely devoid of herpetofaunal remains. Comparing abundance information to radiocarbon dates, correlations can be established between varying abundances and climatic changes related to the Late Pleistocene–Holocene transition.

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Small mammals from cave deposits and paleoclimate reconstructions during the Pleistocene

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Small mammals are a group of fossil fauna important for the understanding of fine-scale responses to environmental change during Pleistocene in Europe. They have rapid generation times and are often found at exceptionally high abundances, making them relatively easy to locate and be captured by predators who nest close to caves entrance or fissures. Rodents also do not migrate seasonally to compensate fluctuating climate and food resources, are resident and mostly do not hibernate, meaning that they respond and adapt to year-round conditions.

Given their geochronological value rodents play an important role in refining biochronostratigraphic scheme of cave deposits. Small mammal paleontology provides relevant information on the chronology of certain climatic phenomena, establishing correlations with other sites located at great distances from each other.

The local evolution of the various species can be integrated into a broader sites network from different regions due to an abundance of information and studies carried out. Together with other proxies, such as isotopic analyses, DNA, pollen etc., their study provides useful tools for the reconstruction of the paleoclimate and paleoenvironment in a wider framework.

Paleontological studies in karst deposits have been carried out since many years ago in southeastern Romania (Dobrogea) and the Carpathians and are ongoing until today, providing rich small mammal associations with many species found outside their present areas of dispersion as a result of climate changes. Karst and cave deposits very often supply abundant remains of small mammals from the middle Pleistocene to Holocene. During the last few years, in order to obtain paleoclimatic reconstructions for the Upper Pleistocene, we have studied a series of sites, such as Bisericuta, Muierilor, Stoieni, Oase, and several caves from the Varghis gorges, sometimes in correlation with archeological excavations. The research, based on a systematic survey of the fossil fauna, revealed the direct relation between climatic events and faunal changes during Pleistocene.

Aspfjordgrotta: a recorder of glacial-interglacial cycles

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Solutional caves are used extensively as proxies to decode landscape evolution through time and to understand different drivers that affected the geomorphology of a given area. Here we present preliminary results of our work on Aspfjordgrotta in Northern Norway. Aspfjordgrotta cave (67°29'N 15°38'E) is situated in low hill, Stortuva, in the southwest-trending valley, Ospfjorrdalen, in Sørfold municipality (150 km east of the southernmost islands of the Lofoten archipelago). Aspfjordelva river drains into Aspfjorden, a small side-fjord of Sørfolda which is part of the Folda fjord system. We study the cave morphology to decode the speleogenetic processes and to define past positions of the ancient water table. We further use the sediment accumulations inside the cave to understand the hydrological regime that enabled the sediment deposition during different glacial cycles. Our research suggests that the cave is formed under phreatic conditions and that the speleogenetic agents were guided by the foliation of the marble in combination with brittle structures. Following the establishment of the cave geometry, Aspfjordgrotta experienced different hydrological settings. These different conditions are evident inside the cave by features that point to extensive sedimentation (paragenetic features, cemented sediment accumulations, epiphreatic features etc) and subsequent sediment removal and abrasion (keyhole passages, breakdowns etc) under vadose conditions. Our findings provide insights of the glacial forcing in cave development and suggest a conceptual speleogenetic model attributing the changes of the hydrological regime to the glacial cycles.

Climatic oscillations of the last 35 ka recorded in sacking deposits of marble stripe karst (Făgăraș Mountains, Southern Carpathians)

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Sackungen are geomorphic features triggered by deep-seated gravitational slope deformations (DSGSDs) in mountain regions, which contain a sedimentary infill with high potential of holding evidence on paleoclimate and landscape evolution. Their proxy record is recognized to successfully supplement the geochronological information from moraine deposits, speleothems, or other climate archives at a particular location. In this study, we investigated for the first time in the Romanian Carpathians the morphology and sedimentary content of a sacking trench formed at ~2260 m a.s.l. in the Făgăraș Mountains, and reported radiocarbon ages dating back to ~35 ka, which were the oldest found for such deposits. The sacking formed along a tectonic fault that cuts the dolomitic marble bedrock perpendicularly to the Mușeteica glacial cirque. Evidence for a tectonic fault origin consists in the sacking morphology (the scarp length to height ratio is >10:1) and the presence of cataclastic breccia. The sediment sampled from the sacking center (PMS1 profile, 1.8-m deep) was analyzed for grain size, organic matter content, and magnetic susceptibility. Four bulk samples were analyzed for AMS ¹⁴C dating. The stratigraphic profile revealed a poorly sorted material, with fine and very fine sands containing sparse fragments of dolomitic marble. A black clay horizon occurred at 70-80 cm below the surface, suggesting a depositional hiatus that separated the sedimentary content of the sacking into two distinct units. The upper part contains mostly lacustrine sediments, and the lower part consists in colluvial deposits overlying a buried talus slope of periglacial origin. A sudden increase of inorganic carbon content and coarse sand, joined by a decrease of organic matter content, magnetic susceptibility, and sorting occurred below the disconformity. The 2σ calibrated ages, reported at a 95.4% probability level, range between 1164 ± 30 calBP yr at the depth of -20 cm, and 34,411 ± 185 calBP yr at -150 cm. The sediment ages below and above the disconformity were 8634 ± 41 and 24,715 ± 94 calBP yr, respectively, suggesting a depositional hiatus of ~16 ka. The sacking functioned as a sediment trap, in close connection with the surrounding karst and glacial landforms. Our preliminary data indicate that sediment deposition occurred mostly during the warm periods of the last 35 ka (MIS 3 and MIS 1), with interruptions caused by glacial activity during the Last Glacial Maximum. These results provided new information on the long-debated timing of glaciation and landscape evolution in the alpine environment of the central Southern Carpathians.

Late Pleistocene climate evolution in the Southern Carpathians recorded by cave deposits from Muierilor cave system (Romania)

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This study presents data on the complex evolution of the Muierilor Cave system, in the Romanian Carpathian Mountains during the Late Pleistocene. The research included paleontological excavations coupled with sedimentological and geomorphological studies and dated through a combination of U/Th, OSL, and radiocarbon techniques. Studied deposits include fossil remains, speleothems, and cave sediments covering a time span from ~120 ka through the Holocene. Within this period, we have identified several evolutive stages of the cave and a succession of paleofloods most likely related to regional climatic changes. As a result, a rich fossil deposit accumulated within the cave passages including Upper Pleistocene fauna typical for the MIS 3-2 suggesting that the Southern Carpathians may have constituted a glacial refugia for the LGM great mammals. The taphonomical study combined with dating of speleothems from stratigraphically-relevant positions indicate that significant sediment inflow in the underground occurred between ~22.5-14.5 ka. This suggests a deglaciation on the southern slopes of the Southern Carpathians that occurred earlier than previously known. The results provide a better understanding of the influences of post-LGM paleofloods on the cave sediments triggered by deglaciation, improves our knowledge about large mammal population dynamics from this region and highlights that the cave system evolution from MIS 5 to the Holocene is closely related to the regional climatic pulses.

Palaeodiet and palaeoecology of a complex Late Pleistocene mammal association in the Romanian Carpathians

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Over the last decades, analysis of the stable isotopes of C and N has been extensively used for palaeodietary reconstruction of the MIS 3 fauna from the Romanian Carpathians. The faunal assemblages from the majority of the well-known cave sites from this region are dominated by bears, thus leaving fewer opportunities for stable isotopic analyses on other taxa. Muierilor Cave (Southern Carpathians), however, is an exception, and has sedimentary deposits that yielded a taxonomically rich Late Pleistocene palaeofauna including red deer, cave bears, cave lions, wolves, and hyenas. $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ and $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values derived from the collagen of 40 mammals from this cave indicated a clear delimitation of dietary behaviors among studied faunas. In addition, herbivores and carnivores from the same bone assemblages display $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ and $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values similar to those of the Central and Western European MIS 3 populations. The richness of the large mammal fauna and the large sample size allowed for a better understanding of the palaeoecological relationships among these species. This study demonstrates the usefulness of $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ and $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ analysis in sites with a complex fossil faunal context and shows a good agreement between the newly obtained data and those reported for other European Late Pleistocene large mammals.

**A high-resolution Holocene speleothem record from Tăușoare Cave, NE Romania:
the nexus of Arctic and North Atlantic atmospheric circulations**

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The Romanian Carpathians act as a geomorphological barrier between different atmospheric circulation systems over Central and Eastern Europe; the NW of Romania lies under the remote influence of the North Atlantic oscillation, while the NE is influenced by the Arctic climate. In NW Romania, previous stable isotope studies of speleothems have not yielded a clear account of abrupt climate oscillations during the Holocene. Here we present results from a stalagmite collected from the Taușoare Cave, located in NE Carpathians. The chronology of stalagmite T141 is based on 15 high-precision Th/U dates ranging between 32 and 1.1 ka with a continuous growth between ~13.3 and 1.1 ka. The portion of the record within the Holocene was analyzed for $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ at a resolution ranging between 15 to 200 years/sample. The resulting $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ record captures the Younger Dryas (YD) event centered at ~12.9 ka, with $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ values about 4 ‰ more depleted than those corresponding to the Holocene Climatic Optimum. The 8.2 ka event appears to be also captured in the record, although less prominent. The T141 isotope record is significantly different when compared to coeval records measured in speleothems from NW Carpathians, which do not exhibit marked changes during the YD or 8.2 ka events. This is likely due to the contrasting effect of temperature and atmospheric transport on $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ signal in NW Romania. Within a distance of 200 km to the east, on the eastern flank of the Carpathian range, the $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ signal of the Arctic circulation appears to be more prominent and clearly exhibits a positive relationship with temperature changes.

Experimental geoelectric measurements carried out in Ursilor Cave (Apuseni Mountains)

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We present the first application of geoelectrical methods in the study of an underground sedimentary deposit in Romania. The measurements were performed in Ursilor Cave (Bihor county), in the first chamber of the "Scientific Reserve", where a systematic paleontological excavation is being carried out.

The main purpose of these investigations was to highlight the thickness of the sediment stack, as well as the lithological variations across the stratigraphic log, partially known thanks to the paleontological excavations. The technique uses the distribution of the values of apparent electrical resistivity (ρ_a) expressed in [$\text{Ohm} \cdot \text{m}$] and induced polarization (IP) expressed in milliradians [mrad].

The geoelectric methods using direct current (DC), were the VES (Vertical Electrical Sounding) and the ERT (Electrical Resistivity Tomography) -- multielectrode combined with IP (Induced Polarization in order to highlight the clays). For both methods, the rectilinear length of the measuring device (Array), which also conditions the depth of investigation, was extremely limited by the small size of the chamber (c. 100 sqm). The two profiles, VES and ERT - IP, respectively the geoelectric sections had a length of 20 m with an approximately north-south orientation.

The investigation depth differs slightly for the two methods: ~5 m for the VES and 3.5-3.6 m for the ERT. The dedicated software used were: WinGlink; Interpex; Res2-3Dinv; GeoTest; with which the 1D and 2D models were generated by using the reversal procedure.

Although the paleontological excavations and the lateral resistivity variations influence the interpretation of the lithology, the following levels of unconsolidated sedimentation can be delimited vertically, along with the presence of limestones (cracked, altered, saturated with water): <50 clays; 50 – 80 sandy clay with fossils; 80 – 130 heterogeneous rock fragments in clayey matrix, alluvium; 130 – 280 saturated altered limestone; >280 wet massive limestones. The values are expressed in [$\text{ohm} \cdot \text{m}$] and represent the apparent resistivity (ρ_a), which at depth correspond to the lithological sequences identified in the excavation.